

$[M(\text{bpy})_2(L^2)]$ complexes in organic solvents is probably due to the presence of two SO_3Na groups in the naphthalene ring. Electronic spectra of $[M(\text{bpy})_2(L^1)]$ and $[M(\text{bpy})_2(L^2)]$ ($M = \text{Ru}$ and Os) were recorded in acetonitrile and aqueous solution respectively. Spectral data are presented in Table 1 and selected spectra are shown in Fig. 1. All these complexes show two intense absorptions in the visible region which are probably due to

Fig. 1. Electronic spectrum of (—) $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(L^1)]$ in acetonitrile solution and (---) $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(L^2)]$ in aqueous solution.

the metal-to-ligand charge-transfer transitions. Multiple charge-transfer transitions in these mixed ligand complexes may result from lower symmetry splitting of the metal level, the presence of different acceptor orbitals and from the mixing of singlet and triplet configurations in the excited state through spin-orbit coupling⁵. For proper assignment of these transitions, qualitative EHMO calculations have been performed⁶ on computer generated models of the $[M(\text{bpy})_2(L^1)]$ complexes. The results of these calculations are very similar for the ruthenium and osmium complexes. Partial MO diagram for the ruthenium complex is shown in Fig. 2. The highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and the next two occupied orbitals (HOMO-1 and HOMO-2) have major (>60%) contributions from the ruthenium orbitals and hence they may be regarded as the metal t_2 orbitals. The lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) and the next unoccupied orbital (LUMO+1) are basically (>90%) π^* -orbitals of the bipyridine ligands. The charge-transfer transitions observed in the visible region may therefore be assigned to transitions occurring from the filled metal t_2 orbitals to the vacant π^* -orbitals of the bipyridine ligands.

Cyclic voltammetric studies : Electron-transfer properties of the $[M(\text{bpy})_2(L^1)]$ and $[M(\text{bpy})_2(L^2)]$ complexes were studied respectively in acetonitrile solution (0.1 M TEAP) and aqueous solution (0.1 M NaClO_4) by cyclic voltammetry. Voltammetric data are presented in Table 1 and selected voltammograms are shown in Fig. 3. Each

Fig. 2. Partial molecular orbital diagram of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(L^1)]$.

$[M(\text{bpy})_2(L^1)]$ complex shows two oxidative responses on the positive side of SCE and two reductive responses on the negative side. In the $[M(\text{bpy})_2(L^2)]$ complexes, only one oxidative response has been observed because of the smaller voltage window offered by water. The first oxidative response, observed within -0.08 to 0.44 V (all potentials are referenced to SCE), is assigned to the $M(\text{II})$ - $M(\text{III})$ oxidation (Eq. 1),

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammogram of (a) $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(L^1)]$ in acetonitrile solution (0.1M TEAP) and (b) $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(L^2)]$ in aqueous solution (0.1M NaClO_4) at a scan rate of 50 mV s^{-1} .

Table 1. Microanalytical, electronic Spectral and cyclic voltammetric data of the complexes^a

Compd.	λ_{\max} , nm (ϵ , $M^{-1}cm^{-1}$)			$E_{298} V(\Delta E_p, mV)^b$		
				$M^{II}-M^{III}$	$M^{III}-M^{IV}$	bpy-reduction
[Ru(bpy) ₂ (L ¹)] ^c	660 ^d (1700), 370 (6700),	550 (5900), 300 (25100)	480 ^d (4300),	0.44 (70) ^e	1.65 ^{e,f}	-1.76 (110) ^e 1.93 ^e
[Os(bpy) ₂ (L ¹)] ^c	640 (300), 400 (3700),	530 ^d (700), 280 (16700)	450 ^d (2200),	-0.08 (80) ^e	1.29 ^{e,f}	-1.83 (100) ^e -2.01 ^e
[Ru(bpy) ₂ (L ²)] ^g	700 (4200), 330 (6800),	470 (5200), 295 (23900)	350 (7100),	0.76 ^{e,h}	-	-
[Os(bpy) ₂ (L ²)] ^g	720 (600), 355 (12800),	530 (1800), 340 (11600),	410 (7150), 290 ^d (17000)	0.44 ^{e,h}	-	-

^aAll compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses. ^b $E_{298} = 0.5 (E_{pa} + E_{pc})$, where E_{pa} and E_{pc} are anodic and cathodic peak potentials respectively $\Delta E_p = E_{pa} - E_{pc}$ in mV; solute concentration, $\sim 10^{-3} M$; scan rate, 50 mV s⁻¹. ^cElectronic spectrum and cyclic voltammetry in acetonitrile solution. ^dShoulder. ^eSupporting electrolyte, TEAP (0.1 M). ^f E_{pa} value. ^gElectronic spectrum and cyclic voltammetry in aqueous solution. ^hSupporting electrolyte, NaClO₄ (0.1 M).

This oxidation is reversible for the [M(bpy)₂(L¹)] complexes, characterized by a peak-to-peak separation (ΔE_p) of 70–80 mV which remains unaltered upon changing the scan rate. The anodic peak current (i_{pa}) is almost equal to the cathodic peak current (i_{pc}), as expected for a reversible couple. The one-electron nature of this oxidation has been established by comparing its current height with that of standard ferrocene/ferrocenium couple under identical experimental conditions. The M(II)-M(III) oxidation potential in [M(bpy)₂]²⁺ is 1.30 V for M = ruthenium⁷ and 0.84 V for M = osmium⁸. In the [M(bpy)₂(L¹)] complexes the same oxidation takes place at 0.44 V and -0.08 V for ruthenium and osmium respectively. This lowering of oxidation potential by -900 mV upon replacement of one bpy by L¹, reflects the ability of this phenolate ligand to stabilize the +3 state of these metals. In the [M(bpy)₂(L²)] complexes this oxidation takes place irreversibly in aqueous solution and one-electron nature of this oxidation has been established by comparing its current height with that of standard [Fe(CN)₆]⁴⁻/[Fe(CN)₆]³⁻ couple under identical experimental conditions. The irreversibility of this oxidation indicates that the oxidized species formed during the anodic scan is very unstable and undergoes fast chemical transformation. The oxidation potential is ~400 mV more positive compared to the corresponding [M^{II}(bpy)₂(L¹)] analogs. The shifting of the oxidation potential is due to the presence of stronger electron-withdrawing SO₃⁻ groups in the naphthalene ring. The positive shift of this oxidation potential indicates that the +2* state of the metals is more stabilized upon coordination by L² compared to that by L¹. Comparison of the ruthenium(II)-ruthenium(III) oxidation potential in the [Ru(bpy)₂(L)] complexes with the osmium(II)-osmium(III) oxidation potential in the corresponding [Os(bpy)₂(L)] complexes shows that the oxidation is much easier in the osmium complexes as usually observed⁹.

The [M(bpy)₂(L¹)] complexes show a second irre-

versible oxidative response (at 1.65 V for M = Ru and at 1.29 V for M = Os) which is assigned to the M(III)-M(IV) oxidation (Eq. 2),

The one-electron nature of this oxidation is established by comparing its current height (i_{pa}) with that of the corresponding M(II)-M(III) couple. Two reductive responses are exhibited by the [M(bpy)₂(L¹)] complexes at potential below -1.7 V which are assigned to reductions of the coordinated bpy ligands (Eqs. 3,4),

It is well documented that each bpy can successively accept two electrons in its lowest unoccupied molecular orbital¹⁰. Hence in these [M(bpy)₂(L¹)] complexes four successive reductions may be expected, of which two have been experimentally observed. The other two reductive responses could not be observed due to the solvent cut-off.

Experimental

Commercial ruthenium trichloride and osmium tetroxide (Arora Matthey, Calcutta) were used. Ruthenium trichloride was converted to RuCl₃·3H₂O by repeated evaporation with concentrated HCl. Osmium tetroxide was converted to (NH₄)₂[OsBr₆] by reduction with HBr¹¹. [Ru(bpy)₂Cl₂] and [Os(bpy)₂Br₂] were synthesized from RuCl₃·3H₂O and (NH₄)₂[OsBr₆] respectively using literature procedures^{12,13}. 1,8-Dihydroxynaphthalene(H₂L¹) was prepared by following a reported procedure¹⁴. 2,2'-Bipyridine (bpy) and 1,8-dihydroxynaphthalene-3,6-disulphonic acid disodium salt (H₂L²) were purchased from Loba Chemie, Mumbai. All other chemicals and solvents were reagent grade and used as received. Purification of acetonitrile and preparation of tetraethylammonium perchlorate (TEAP) for electrochemical work were performed as reported in the literature¹⁵.

$[Ru(bpy)_2(L^1)]$: To a mixture of $[Ru(bpy)_2Cl_2]$ (100 mg, 0.19 mmol) and H_2L^1 (34 mg, 0.21 mmol) taken in ethanol (40 cm³), triethylamine (0.06 cm³, 0.42 mmol) was added. The solution was refluxed for 6 h under N₂ atmosphere. The volume of the solvent was then reduced to ~10 cm³ and kept in a refrigerator for 12 h. A dark coloured microcrystalline solid that separated out was washed with water and dried under reduced pressure over P₄O₁₀. It was recrystallized from 1 : 1 acetonitrile-benzene solution, yield 64 mg (58%).

$[Os(bpy)_2(L^1)]$: It was synthesized by using the above procedure using $[Os(bpy)_2Br_2]$ (100 mg, 0.15 mmol), 2-methoxyethanol (35 cm³) and triethanolamine (0.05 cm³, 0.32 mmol) instead of $[Ru(bpy)_2Cl_2]$, ethanol and triethylamine respectively, yield 55 mg (55%).

$[Ru(bpy)_2(L^2)]$: A mixture of $[Ru(bpy)_2Cl_2]$ (100 mg, 0.19 mmol), H_2L^2 (77 mg, 0.19 mmol), ethanol (30 cm³) and triethylamine (0.06 cm³, 0.42 mmol) was refluxed for 5 h under N₂ atmosphere. Volume of the solvent was then reduced to ~5 cm³. After being cooled to room temperature, a saturated aqueous solution of NaClO₄ (1 cm³) was added to it followed by acetone (100 cm³) to precipitate out a greenish brown solid. The solid was washed several times with acetone, dried in air and recrystallized from water-acetonitrile solution to give $[Ru(bpy)_2(L^2)]$ as a microcrystalline solid, yield 118 mg (79%).

$[Os(bpy)_2(L^2)]$: $[Os(bpy)_2(L^2)]$ was synthesized by using the same above procedure using $[Os(bpy)_2Br_2]$ (100 mg, 0.15 mmol), 2-methoxyethanol (35 cm³) and triethanolamine (0.05 cm³, 0.32 mmol) instead of $[Ru(bpy)_2Cl_2]$, ethanol and triethylamine respectively, yield 100 mg (76%).

Microanalyses (C, H, N) were performed using a Perkin-Elmer 240C elemental analyser. Ir spectra (KBr) were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a Shimadzu UV 240 spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility was measured using a PAR 155 magnetometer. Electrochemical measurement was made using a PAR 273 potentiostat under N₂-atmosphere. A Pt-disc working electrode, a Pt-wire auxiliary electrode and an aqueous saturated calomel reference electrode (SCE) were used in a three-electrode configuration. A RE0074 X-Y recorder was used to trace the voltammogram. All electrochemical data were collected at 289 K and uncorrected for junction potentials.

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